

FLOATFARM
NEXT GENERATION FLOATING WIND FARMS

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Validation and Testing of Radar Wave Sensing on Floatgen

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Full name
RAO	Response Amplitude Operator
FOWT	Floating Offshore Wind Turbine
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
DOF	Degree of Freedom
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
GPS	Global Positioning System
BEM	Boundary Element Method
QTF	Quadratic Transfer Function

ABOUT FLOATFARM

The FLOATFARM project is a Research and Innovation Action funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe program. This project is closely linked to the FLOATECH project (2020-2023) and aims to bring the technologies developed within [FLOATECH](#) to the next level of technological readiness, complementing them with a significant number of new concepts, innovations and methods.

FLOATFARM aims to significantly advance the maturity and competitiveness of floating offshore wind (FOW) technology by increasing energy production, achieving significant cost reductions within the design and implementation phases, improving offshore wind value chain and supporting EU companies in this growing sector. Additionally, FLOATFARM aims to decrease negative environmental impacts on marine life and to enhance the public acceptability of FOW, thereby accelerating the EU energy transition.

The FLOATFARM consortium is coordinated by the Technische Universität Berlin and is made up of 17 partners spread across 8 countries, each contributing to technology and scientific excellence in the wind energy sector.

The approach of FLOATFARM can be broken down into three actions:

- 1) **Turbine Technology:** Development of innovative technologies and methods for improvements on an individual FOW turbine level,
- 2) **Farm Technology:** Development, investigation and demonstration of technologies that are applicable to an array of turbines within a FOW farm,
- 3) **Environmental & Socioeconomic Impacts:** Model development, data collection and scenario analysis of environmental, economic and sociological impacts of FOW farms.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Next Ocean's contribution to Offshore Wind

Floating wind turbine technology comes with different challenges compared to conventional bottom founded offshore wind, both in the Transport and Installation (T&I) and Operation and Maintenance (O&M) phase. Next Ocean addresses and aims to contribute to solutions to some of these challenges, the most important of which are:

- Turbine access; transfer of cargo and crew from Construction Service Operation Vessels ((C)SOV's) or Crew Transfer Vessels (CTV's), can be challenging. Next Ocean's vessel motion prediction technology indicates safe working windows ahead of time (~1–3 minutes in advance) during which wave induced vessel motions will be within operational limits for compensated gangway transfers from SOV or bow step over from CTV to turbine, enabling safe operation, also in marginal conditions. This turbine access challenge will be more pronounced for floating turbines.
- Control; control of floating wind turbines comes with additional challenges compared to bottom founded turbines. Wave induced motions introduce additional degrees of freedom. Anticipating to wave effects by means of control feedforward, enabled by predictive technology such as Next Ocean's has been addressed in this project's predecessor 'Floatech', and its advancement will be the focus of Next Ocean's contribution to this project.

1.2. Wave feed-forward control for floating wind turbines

Wave feedforward control to improve the performance of floating wind turbines by predicting wave excitation forces and compensating for wave-induced disturbances was explored in (Hegazy, et al., 2023). By predicting wave excitation forces using radar measurements of incoming waves, the system proactively adjusts the turbine's blade pitch to reduce unwanted rotor speed fluctuations and platform motions. This approach enhances the turbine's stability and power quality, especially in challenging offshore environments. The results show that feedforward control based on wave excitation force prediction can improve the performance compared to traditional feedback-only methods, making it a promising technology for future floating wind energy systems.

In (Hegazy, et al., 2024), a wave tank experiment, explained in (Bonney, et al., 2024), was conducted to assess the potential of the wave feedforward technology, where real-time wave excitation previews were integrated into the control loop. Overall, this experiment underscores the practical benefits of wave force prediction-based control to enhance power quality and turbine stability in offshore environments.

1.3. Project scope

The scope of Next Ocean's contribution to Work Package 1 of the Floatfarm project focusses on the demonstration and validation of wave excitation force prediction for the use within feed forward applications as described in the previous paragraph. It builds upon previous work in Floatech, using experimental data from a field campaign which was carried out on board BW Ideol's floating turbine 'Floatgen', located at Ecole Centrale Nantes founded test-site SEM-REV, located 20 km off the coast from Le Croisic, France. During this campaign a wave radar was mounted on Floatgen's turbine pile, acquiring radar data and data from additional onboard sensors, among which a 6 DOF motion sensor. Within Floatech, Next Ocean performed analysis leading to a comparison of wave elevation predictions obtained from its wave radar technology and measurement by a buoy moored in the vicinity of the Floatgen platform. An advancement of this analysis and validation towards the wave excitation on the platform is the main topic for this project.

2. Approach

2.1. Introduction

As mentioned, the main aim of the project work is to demonstrate and validate the prediction of wave excitation forces by deterministic (i.e. phase resolved) wave radar technology. Wave excitation force is a convenient control input as compared to e.g. wave elevation, since it inherently includes the information about wave directionality. However, validation of the predicted excitation force is not trivial: Under the assumption that it can be considered as independent from the resulting motion response, as is done in the linear wave-motion response model, captive tests can be performed to directly measure the excitation force. However, this is obviously only feasible in model experiments.

At full scale, there's no other option than an indirect approach where the *motions* caused by the excitation force are predicted, which can then be compared against a measurement of these motions. This is the approach followed in this work.

The underlying assumption to justify this approach is that from obtaining an accurate prediction of the wave induced floater motion, it is fair to conclude that it resulted from an also accurate prediction of the excitation force. Although in theory, an error in the excitation force prediction could be partly compensated by an error in the model that translates this excitation force to motion response, this assumption is considered justified.

The case where motion response prediction is *not* accurate, leads to a different consideration: floater motion dynamics depends on more than just excitation forces by the waves, partly being related to hydromechanics reactions (hydromechanical mass, damping and restoring), structural mass and inertia, wind induced forces and mooring forces.

How these factors and the way they are modelled possibly affects the validation results will be briefly addressed in the following paragraphs.

2.2. Prediction Model

2.2.1. Incoming wave prediction

A linear directional wave model, existing of a summation of sinusoidal wave components, each having a distinct combination of frequency and propagation direction, is initialized from the radar images. After initialization, the waves arriving in the future at the buoy or floater platform can be predicted. More details on this model can be found in (Wijaya, et al., 2015)

Especially for the predictions of the wave elevation at the buoy, the target location for which the future incoming wave is predicted is not fixed. This is clearly illustrated by Figure 3-4, where the right-hand side image shows the large displacements, the buoy apparently makes over the course of an hour. For this reason, buoy predictions are generated by using the exact future buoy position (which for real-time live application would obviously not be possible).

2.2.2. Motion modelling

The interaction between the linear wave model and the vessel was modelled via linear transfer functions, obtained from a potential flow Boundary Element Model (BEM). See e.g. (Kurnia & Ducrozet , 2023) for both theory on potential flow BEM's in general and one in particular that has been used in this work.

2.2.3. Mooring effects

Stiffness provided by mooring effects is assumed to be sufficiently low to significantly affect the wave induced 1st order motions. Indications that this assumption is justified can be found in Figure 3-9, which shows that the frequency of the motions in the horizontal plane is well below the frequency band containing wave energy.

Given the lay out of the mooring system (see Figure 3-2) with taut lines in only ~34 m water depth, the stiffness in vertical direction will be even lower, and can again be safely assumed not to interfere with the frequency band of the 1st order motions. The generally very high accuracy found for the heave predictions of the platform, obtained by using motion transfer functions indeed ignoring the mooring system, is another indication that this assumption is justified.

2.2.4. Wind effects

Wind has a critical effect on the global dynamics of wind turbines. However, it normally operates within a different frequency range than waves as shown in Figure 2-1. Kaimal spectrum (Kaimal, et al., 1972) was used for wind with a mean wind speed of 8 m/s that is relevant to site of interest according to the Global Wind Atlas. The equation for Kaimal spectrum reads (Jonkman, 2009):

$$S_u(f) = \frac{4\sigma_u^2 L_u / \bar{U}_{hub}}{(1 + 6f L_u / \bar{U}_{hub})^{5/3}}, \quad \sigma_u = I * \bar{U}_{hub},$$

where σ_u is the standard deviation of the wind speed, L_u is the turbulence length scale, f is the frequency, and \bar{U}_{hub} is the mean wind speed at the hub.

As for the waves, JONSWAP spectrum was used with a significant wave height of 3 m according to Météo-France and Service Hydrographique et Océanographique de la Marine (SHOM).

Figure 2-1: Operational frequency bands of the wind and wave spectra

Figure 2-1 demonstrates how the wind and waves exist in different frequency bands, as wind-driven response is found at very low frequencies in comparison to the wave-driven response at higher frequencies. For the waves, two peak periods of 5 s and 15 s are shown to depict how the wave energy varies across the wind sea frequency range as at the lower frequencies, the wave energy is concentrated about the peak period as for the case of 5 s, while it disperses at higher frequencies as observed in the 15 s case.

3. Experimental set-up

3.1. Test Site

The field experiment, executed within the scope of Floatfarm predecessor Floatech took place on the French offshore test site SEM-REV managed by Ecole Centrale de Nantes¹, and dedicated to test Marine Renewable Energy (MRE) devices and components at sea.

SEM-REV site is located offshore Le Croisic, approximately 12 nm from continental shore. SEM-REV maritime area is bounded by a square of about 1 km², holding a concession to occupy the public domain for the specific purpose of MRE tests since 2011. A power export cable and a subsea hub have been laid on site and the export cable is connected to an

¹ SEM-REV operation was conducted under ECN management at the time of the experiment. SEM-REV is now transferred to Fondation OPEN-C since 01/09/2023.

onshore station, enabling connection to the French National Distribution grid. Four special marks buoys located at each corner of the test site are identifying SEM-REV area at sea.

Figure 3-1, SEM-REV test site location

SEM-REV is hosting the Floatgen Project², a prototype of floating offshore wind turbine developed by BW Ideol, anchored on site and connected to the grid since 2018. The prototype is a platform for satellite partnership research projects since then.

Figure 3-2 shows the location and orientation of the Floatgen FOWT and its mooring system and indicates the location of the buoys moored at the test site. For this project, as was the case for Floatech, data from the buoy indicated with “Houlo_ouest_2” was used for reference.

² EU FP7 FLOATGEN Project - <https://floatgen.eu>

Figure 3-2, Site Occupancy from July 2022 to March 2023, dedicated to Floatech Experiment

3.2. Wave Radar

The wave radar set-up involves a radar antenna mounted at the turbine tower

The radar turning unit and antenna are placed approximately 16 meters above sea level, located at the top of the transition piece of the wind turbine. The radar is a 10kW Sperry Marine X-band radar, with an 8 feet vertically polarized antenna. This setup was mounted on an aluminum pedestal, specially designed and manufactured for this project and mounted in such a way that the radar antenna was facing in south-south-westerly direction in order to enable to observe incoming waves for the predominant wave direction at the site. Figure 3-3 shows pictures of the radar mounted to the turbine pile of Floatgen

A sample of an acquired radar image is shown in Figure 3-4.

Figure 3-3, Wave Radar mounted to Floatgen turbine pile

Figure 3-4, example radar image and wave buoy location (I), zoomed in on buoy position (r)

3.3. Floater Motion Sensing

A motion sensor (IMU, brand SBG) is part of the permanently installed equipment on board of Floatgen. Its location relative to the reference axes system depicted in Figure 3-5 was determined at: $(x,y,z) = (4.426, -2.58, 11.068)$ [m].

Figure 3-5, Floatgen axes reference system

3.3.1. Recorded motions in vertical plane

Raw IMU signals require signal processing in order to provide the actual translational (surge, sway and heave) and rotational (roll, pitch and yaw) motion displacements. Absolute motions in the horizontal plane require additional information / analyses which is not part of the output for the IMU as installed on board Floatgen. However, when it is the *fluctuation* about a mean position that is of interest, where the absolute value of the mean

position is not specifically relevant, horizontal motions can be obtained from integration of the raw translational acceleration signals and the rotational gyro signals. For the vertical motions, these integrations are processed real-time on board the IMU's software. The real time aspect makes this integration however more difficult. In cases where a delay is no objection, which is the case here since the motion measurements only purpose is validation of the motion predictions, a relatively easy spectral integration based on fft's can be applied

Figure 3-6 shows a typical example of a comparison of spectra of the direct real time output ('native', blue) for those DOF's for which they are available (being heave, roll and pitch) and the result from the spectral integration ('spectral integration', black). The spectrum of the recorded waves is also shown by the dashed line. This wave spectrum is normalized for confidentiality reasons.

It can be observed that the motion spectra match well, except for the low frequency ($\omega < \sim 0.3$) content appearing only for the spectral integration result. Since there's no energy in the recorded wave spectrum in that frequency band, it is concluded that this observed energy is not related to actual (1st order) motions.

It is therefore assumed to be the result of an artifact in the raw acceleration and gyro output of the IMU. A possible candidate is aliasing due to under sampling. However, since the IMU was not part of the Next Ocean set-up and therefore not easily subjected to further investigation, it was decided to use the native motion output from the IMU where possible, i.e. for the vertical motions heave, roll and pitch.

Figure 3-6, spectra of recorded heave (top: 'mot.3'), roll (middle: 'mot.4') and pitch (bottom: 'mot.5') motions. Native sensor output (blue) and integrated raw gyro and acceleration signals (black), together with recorded wave spectrum (dashed). The vertical red line indicates the *computed* (see paragraph 4.6) natural frequency.

3.3.2. Recorded motions in horizontal plane

At the absence of an alternative, for surge, sway and yaw, the motions following from spectral integration were used, with the side note that their accuracy can be questioned based on the above considerations. Example spectra for the motions in the horizontal plane are provided by Figure 3-7.

Given the fact that for the motions in the vertical plane obtained by the spectral integrations (Figure 3-6), energy was found in a frequency band well below the frequency band with significant wave energy, for which no physical explanation can be given, the low frequency content for the obtained motion spectra for the motions in the horizontal plane (Figure 3-7) is considered suspicious.

Figure 3-7, spectra of recorded surge (top), sway (middle) and yaw (bottom) motions. Native sensor output (blue) and integrated raw gyro and acceleration signals (black)

To shine more light on this issue, longitude and latitude recordings from the platform’s GPS sensor were translated into x (east) and y (north) displacements and examined. Time traces are shown in Figure 3-8.

Figure 3-8, Time traces of x (east bound) and y (north bound) platform displacements from GPS position recordings

The corresponding spectra are shown in Figure 3-9. The main energy in the spectra appears in the frequency band well below 0.1 rad/s, which is well below the frequency band under suspicion.

Figure 3-9, Spectra of east- (top) and north-bound (bottom) floater motions obtained from GPS signals

Despite the poor sampling rate (1 Hz) and precision (~10 cm) of the position signal, the x-displacement (top graph in Figure 3-9) seems to pick up some energy close to the

frequency at which the peak in the wave spectrum occurs (around 0.4 – 0.45 rad/s, see dashed lines in Figure 3-7). This gives reason to assume that in case the suspicious energy observed in the motion spectra (Figure 3-6 and Figure 3-7) was related to actually occurring motions, it would have shown up in the spectra from the GPS positions (Figure 3-9).

This is interpreted as another indication that the content in the IMU motion recordings under examination (around the peak at ~0.2 rad/s, Figure 3-6 and Figure 3-7) is not related to actual physical motions but the result of a sensor artifact.

3.3.3. Filtering of motion signals

A band-pass filter was applied to the recorded motion signals with high-pass and low-pass cut-off frequencies set to 0.3 and 2.0 rad/s respectively.

The low pass cut off frequency is chosen based on the floater motion transfer functions that show little to no content above 2.0 rad/s as can be seen in paragraph 4.6.

A brief justification for the choice for the high-pass cut-off frequency will be given here. See Figure 3-10 which presents for each hour the lowest frequency in the recorded wave spectrum at the buoy, below which max. 5% of the total energy in the recorded wave spectrum is represented. Also indicated are the high-pass cut off frequency applied to the directional wave spectra as obtained from the radar data and the high-pass cut off frequency applied to the recorded motions.

Figure 3-10, Lowest observed frequencies in recorded wave elevation by buoy

As can be seen there’s a small number of hours where low frequency energy was found in the wave spectrum obtained by the buoy, at a frequency band below the cut off frequency

applied to the radar spectrum. This indicates that these cases contained (swell) waves which were not taken into account by the wave and motion prediction.

Figure 3-11 shows 1D wave spectra from radar and wave buoy and 2D spectra from the radar for a simple uni-modal wave spectrum (top), a combined sea-swell spectrum (middle) and a combined sea-swell spectrum where the swell is missed by the radar because of filter settings (bottom).

However, since for the vast majority of the investigated hours of data the lowest observed frequency in the recorded wave data at the buoy was well above the cut-off frequencies of both radar spectra and recorded motion spectra, the chosen filter settings were considered to be appropriate.

Figure 3-11, Samples of 1D spectra from radar and buoy (left) and directional wave spectra (right)

4. Results & Discussion

This chapter presents and discusses the accuracy of the predictions of the floater motions as obtained from analysis of the radar data.

4.1. Data selection

A dataset was selected existing of ~230 hours of synchronized radar, floater motion, floater heading, floater GPS, and motion sensor data recorded over the fall of 2022.

Criteria for selection of these hours were:

- data availability; data acquisition was interrupted several times as a result of power cuts on board the Floatgen platform, after which manual reset and restart of the radar system was required because of safety requirements
- data interruptions; hours in which short data interruptions occurred were discarded
- minimum wave height; hours with H_s lower than 0.75 m were discarded
- minimum wind speed; hours with wind speed lower than 3 m/s were discarded
- peak wave direction coming from visible sector (see Figure 3-4); as mentioned the visible azimuths by the radar were limited to a sector of 160 degrees size facing south-west. only hours for which the peak wave direction was in this sector were analyzed

4.2. Quantification of prediction accuracy

In order to quantify the accuracy of the motion predictions, we use the Pearson correlation coefficient, defined as:

$$corr. = \frac{\sum(x - \bar{x}) \cdot (y - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (1)$$

where upper bar denotes the mean value.

This accuracy quantification is especially discriminative regarding correct phasing of the two signals under comparison, which is considered as specifically relevant for control purposes. The product of the standard deviations in the denominator removes sensitivity to correct amplitude. Since real time scaling of predicted signals with observed standard deviation over an appropriate history of the measured signal can be used to 'ensure' correct energy of the predicted signal, it is considered appropriate to assess the prediction accuracy with a focus on phasing.

Figure 4-1 shows for all the considered hours of data the correlation between the predicted and recorded floater motions taken over each separate hour (y-axis) and the correlation between the predicted and recorded wave elevation at the buoy (x-axis).

For the wave elevation, it is the 'now-cast' (i.e. 'prediction' 0 s into the future) that is considered, for which in almost all cases the 'prediction' accuracy is the highest. This can be explained by the fact that the buoy is located within the range of vision of the radar, see Figure 3-4. Contrarily, because of the blind range between the radar antenna and the closest observation points of the radar, the *motion* prediction accuracy is not necessarily highest for the now-cast but for significantly longer prediction times, caused by the fact the observed waves need time to travel towards the platform. Therefore, for the motion predictions, the correlation for the prediction horizon yielding the highest correlation is considered, which varied a bit from hour to hour and occasionally showed values up to 120 s. For control purposes prediction time is not considered to be a critical parameter though: a prediction time of 10 s, which is the minimum that was considered in the search for the optimum prediction time, is considered to be sufficient.

4.3. Difference between motion and wave prediction accuracy

As can be seen in Figure 4-1, for the symmetrical motions (i.e. symmetrical with respect to x-z plane being heave, roll and pitch, see Figure 3-5) the motion prediction accuracy is in general significantly higher than the wave prediction accuracy. Especially heave motion prediction is for many hours very accurate with correlation values up to 0.97.

Figure 4-1, Correlation of Floater motion prediction vs wave prediction at buoy

In order to enable a more physical/visual interpretation of the correlation values, sample time are presented in Figure 4-2 (Wijaya, et al., 2015) for the hours indicated with red circles in Figure 4-1 for the heave case.

Figure 4-2, Sample time traces for different prediction accuracies

As can be seen, heave motion predictions are more accurate than the remaining degrees of freedom for the vertical plane, being roll and pitch. A possible explanation for this is the fact that for this particular floater shape, the motion response is more dominated by resonance effects for pitch and roll compared to heave, which seems to be more severely damped and more dominated by excitation. Inaccuracies in e.g. mass moment of inertia therefore could have more impact on the motion transfer functions (see paragraph 4.6) for roll and pitch. (Apart from this, the mass affecting the heave transfer functions is easier to determine in the first place.)

The fact that motions appear to be predicted more accurately than waves can be expected: the floater acts as a low pass filter, leading to a much smaller spectral bandwidth. The shorter waves, which can be expected the most challenging as their relative propagation time and distance are larger and observation requires higher resolution and precision, are not relevant for the floater motions. Accuracy is therefore much more governed by the longer waves whose prediction can be expected to be more accurate. Figure 4-3 illustrates this difference in spectral band width by presenting example spectra of measured waves and measured motions for one sample hour.

Figure 4-3, spectra of recorded motions (right-hand axis) and wave elevation at buoy (left-hand axis)

In an attempt to quantify the relation between spectral band width and prediction accuracy, Figure 4-4 was generated. It presents the spectral bandwidth on the x-axes, defined as the lowest frequency up to which the spectrum of the considered motions or waves contains at least 95% of the spectral energy and the correlation of the motion or wave prediction on the y axis. As can be seen vague trends towards decreasing correlation with increasing spectral band width can be observed, but overall there’s a quite some scatter, indicating that more factors are at play when it comes to prediction accuracy than just spectral band width.

Figure 4-4, prediction correlation vs spectral bandwidth

4.4. Anti-symmetrical motions

As can be seen in Figure 4-1, the prediction of the anti-symmetrical motions (sway, roll and yaw) is significantly less accurate. There’s a few indications we can give that provide part of the explanation for this observation.

First of all it should be noted that because of the requirement that incoming waves are visible to the radar, the selected set of hours only represents wave directions that are coming towards roughly the bow of the floater, as a result of which sway, roll and yaw motion intensity is simply lower. This is illustrated by Figure 4-5 which shows the standard deviation of the motions taken over each hour against correlation of the motion prediction.

Figure 4-5, Standard deviation of measured motions against correlation

Surge shows in general higher standard deviations of the recorded motions than sway. Same can be said about pitch and roll. Regarding yaw recorded motion standard deviations are very low, never exceeding 0.2 deg, which raises questions about the signal to noise ratio.

Moreover, keeping in mind the observed issue with the measurement of the motions in the horizontal plane, as addressed in paragraph 3.3.2, it was decided to consider the yaw case as too cumbersome to further investigate.

4.5. Directional visibility

Based on the directional wave spectrum as estimated from the wave radar, the relative amount of wave energy represented by the waves that could be observed while propagating towards the platform was determined. The so-called directional visibility was computed for this purpose which is defined as the relative amount of energy in the directional spectrum within the sector between the two edges of the visible part of the radar images i.e. the unshaded part of the spectrum in 4.5.

Figure 4-6, Directional visibility

As illustrated by 4.6, some of the cases where a low motion prediction correlation was found are associated with wave conditions with a significantly lower directional visibility.

Figure 4-7, directional visibility of incoming waves vs correlation of motion prediction (using NEMOH motion transfer functions)

4.6. Motion transfer function comparison

The motion RAOs (Response Amplitude Operator) of the vessel (i.e. floating platform) play a crucial role in predicting deterministic vessel motions. BW Ideol provided the hydrodynamic coefficients of their platform that were computed using the BEM (Boundary

Element Method) solver; ANSYS AQWA. Upon using those RAOs from AQWA to obtain the deterministic motion predictions, the motion prediction accuracy was lower than that of the wave prediction. Such performance led to the step of suspecting the motion RAOs. Accordingly, it was decided to reproduce those RAOs using the open-source BEM solver; NEMOH.

NEMOH, developed at École Centrale de Nantes, was the first open-source potential flow BEM solver (Barbarit & Delhommeau, 2015). It is a BEM code dedicated to the computation of first order wave loads on offshore structures (added mass, radiation damping, diffraction forces), with a new extension module for the computation of second-order wave loads through computing Quadratic Transfer Functions (QTFs) (Kurnia & Ducrozet, 2023).

To do the hydrodynamic analysis, the mesh of the vessel, shown in Figure 4-8, was extracted from the ANSYS AQWA output file such that we have an identical mesh, which is composed of 1615 panels. Additionally, it ensured that the inertia and hydrostatic stiffness matrices were similar, as well as solving for the 6 Degrees of Freedom (DOFs) of the platform. However, the frequency resolution was much higher in NEMOH with 200 frequencies compared to 41 frequencies in AQWA as explained in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparison between the settings of AQWA and NEMOH

BEM Solver	No. of panels	No. of frequencies	Frequency sampling	DOF	No. of wave directions
AQWA	1615	41	Variable	6	17
NEMOH	1615	200	Uniform	6	17

Figure 4-8: Visualisation of the mesh for the BW Ideol platform as modelled in AQWA and NEMOH

It is fair to mention that there is difference in the panel geometry each solver uses. As for AQWA, it uses allows using quadrilateral and triangular mesh. However, NEMOH only allows quadrilateral panels (Kurnia & Ducrozet , 2023). As a result, the mesh extracted from AQWA was adapted to be used in NEMOH.

4.6.1. Motion prediction accuracy dependence on transfer function

In this section, we compare the RAOs obtained from NEMOH to the ones from AQWA for different wave headings including beam, quartering and head waves in the 6 DOFs of the floating platform. It should be mentioned that only the case of the quartering waves is shown here, while the remaining two are in the Appendix.

Figure 4-9: Comparison between the RAO computed by NEMOH and AQWA for a wave heading of 135 deg.

Looking at Figure 4-9, we can observe the comparison between the results of both solvers. Generally, there is an agreement in the results for both the RAOs and the phases. There exist some differences, as for instance, there is a difference in the peak amplitude of the heave RAO at a frequency just before 1 rad/s. There is also a difference in the yaw RAO in the low-frequency band. As for the phase, we observe a good agreement till almost 1.5 rad/s or a little bit higher.

It is believed that the reason for those differences might refer to the fact that NEMOH has a higher frequency resolution, making it possible to better catch the peaks in the RAO. Furthermore, NEMOH applies a uniform frequency sampling, thus, has a fixed sampling frequency. Meanwhile AQWA computations were performed with a variable sampling frequency. Moreover, the difference between the panel types of the mesh used in each solver, and the mesh adaptation that has been applied might also be one of the reasons for those deviations in the results.

The reader is referred to the Appendix for the head and beam wave cases at wave headings 180° and 90°, respectively.

Figure 4-10, comparison of motion prediction correlations generated with AQWA and NEMOH motion transfer functions

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

It has been shown that prediction of floater motions can reach accuracies up to 0.97, and it is therefore assumed that predictions of excitation forces can also reach very high accuracy. Motion predictions have been in general found to be significantly more accurate than wave predictions.

However, a large scatter in the motion prediction accuracy is observed. It is therefore recommended that in real-time control applications, the quality of the prediction is constantly monitored (e.g. by monitoring the correlation between measured and predicted motions) and inform the controller about this accuracy in order to use appropriate controller gain values.

Some factors that have shown a clear effect on motion prediction accuracy:

- The considered motion DOF: heave yields more accurate results than roll and pitch. A likely explanation is the fact that heave is in this case more dominated by excitation.
- Spectral band width: motion predictions are found to be more accurate than wave predictions, which can be explained from the narrower response spectrum for floater motions, which are not affected by the shorter waves
- Directional visibility: the incoming waves from all directions need to be observable by the wave sensor

We acknowledge that this list of factors does not provide all relevant explanations for the large variety of prediction accuracies observed and additional research is needed in order to extend this list.

Regarding the application of wave prediction feed-forward for wind turbine control, a crucial research aspect still has to be addressed, which is the question “how the controller should act upon uncertainties in the provided predictions (of e.g. wave excitation force)?”. In practice, the accuracy of the wave prediction introduces uncertainty to the wind turbine system. Dynamic uncertainty refers to the time-varying deviation between the actual disturbance and its predicted value. Since the preview is not perfectly accurate, this uncertainty evolves over time and is typically modelled as a bounded or stochastic signal with its own dynamics. To ensure robust performance, the feedforward controller must be synthesised while accounting for this dynamic uncertainty, which reflects the real-time variability and limited reliability of the disturbance forecast.

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